

TRACES: memories - emotions - stories - objects
Abstract

Aims:

- To devise new pathways to the creation of evocative artifacts that connect owners of the objects to revered memories and traces of identity.
- To engage concepts from psychology, cognitive neuroscience, anthropology, art history, material culture and consumer studies in order to frame a research methodology applied to art, craft and design projects.
- To create evocative objects in bespoke settings, for collective community projects and for more universal distribution.

Research Questions:

- Can a narrative craft object successfully capture emotions defining a person's character when the emotions belong to the future owner of the artifact and not the maker?
- Can the owner's memory stories reveal enough information to inform future artifacts?
- Can the artist/maker interpret this information into a new language meaningful for the future owner whilst expressing her artistic identity and integrity.

Key issues:

- Defining memory for purposes of the research.
- Devising and refining methods to tap into evocative memory stories.
- Developing strategies for interpreting those memories into object form.

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OBJECT AS PORTRAITS: FUTURE OWNERS OF OBJECTS AS SITTERS

Object portraiture: Example:

Your Story/White Blackbird, John Gibbons 2008-9

Role of Sitter in Portraiture:

Irving Penn:
"In portrait photography, there is something more profound we seek inside a person."

Study for Head of Lucien Freud, Arthur Dove 1924

Lucien Freud:
"The model should only serve the very private function for the painter of providing the starting point for his excitement."

Francis Bacon:
"When you paint anything, you are also painting not only the subject, but also you are painting yourself as well as the object... Painting is pure intuition..."

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QUESTION 1: How can object portraits capture the sitters' features?

SITTERS' FEATURES = AUTOBIOGRAPHICAL MEMORY

Autobiographical memory (AM): individual collection of critical personal stories – experienced, told, or compiled, integral to identity. Stories contain interior features serving as inspiration for object portraits.

Schank, R. C. and Abelson, R. P. (1995) Knowledge and Memory: The Real Story in Van Dine, R. S. (ed) Knowledge and Memory: The Real Story Advances in Social Cognitive Volume II (p. 1-52) (New: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates) (p. 5-6).

Cues	Trigger	Indexed Memory Stories
New Memories Collected	Old Memories Collected	Dynamic Sculptor-Identity

AM composed of "scripts", dynamic frameworks into which existing memories collected and new memories collated.

Story-based memory critical for identity development.
Retrieval of memory via memory indexing: links or cues layered onto the structure of the basic stories.
Objects are common memory story cues.

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QUESTION 2: What makes objects memory triggers for sitters – or what is an Evocative Object?

EVOCATIVE OBJECTS AND AUTOBIOGRAPHICAL MEMORY

Cherished objects, often otherwise mundane, contain autobiographical memories by associations with events, places or people or nostalgia for the past, real or imagined. These extraordinary "ordinary" objects become evocative – emotionally durable objects in our lives.

Turkle, Sherry (ed) (2007) Evocative Objects, Things We Think With (Cambridge Mass: MIT Press)

Heirlooms are receptacles of a cultures' collective memory, transmitting significant cross-generational cultural and societal stories. They embed the tales and myths of prior generations and become part of the individual's autobiographical memory.

Emotionally Durable Object

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Evocative Objects : Props to our Indexed Story Scripts

This project is creating new props to enhance sitters' lives by their ability to trigger identity reinforcing stories.

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QUESTION 3: How can one create new props OR how can a new object be evocative?

CREATING NEW OBJECTS AS CUES FOR MEMORY STORIES

Develop methods to trigger sitters' critical memory stories and extract essential elements of stories.

Use these elements to inform the new object portrait, which in turn will trigger the memory stories.

METHODS FOR TRIGGERING STORIES: AIMS 1

- Find repeating patterns of emotions or character to inspire creation of object.

METHODS AIMS 2:

- Find a prototypical story that itself can illustrate sitter's life patterns in such a way as to recall significant moments.
- Draw upon this story for inspiration for object creation.

METHODS AIMS 3:

- Find elements of a story or stories that illustrate concerns impacting across a population group, having universal resonance.
- Draw upon these to move from a bespoke object to creation of objects inspired by "sitters" but intended for wider distribution.

Tapping into sitters' autobiographical memory stories and using these as the inspirational source for object creation provides an emotional link between sitter and artist.

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QUESTION 4: How can the methods be linked to autobiographical memory?

USING SENSORY STIMULI TO TRIGGER MEMORY STORIES

The Limbic System and the particular areas in the brain comprising the Limbic System and associated with Autobiographical Memory and Emotion are also involved in processing certain sensory information.

Hippocampus: the area in the brain known as the memory center is activated in response to certain auditory stimulation.

Amygdala: the area in the brain responsible for processing of emotions.

As proven by fMRI studies:
Olfactory system: simplest of the sensory systems - most closely connected to the amygdala-hippocampus area of the limbic system, processing both emotions and memory.

Methods using sensory stimuli are specifically designed to activate the limbic system, thereby triggering emotionally significant autobiographical memory stories.

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TRANSLATING STORIES INTO OBJECTS

Methods: test diverse sensory stimuli to engage sitter's memory stories: music and sound, touch, smell and taste, and visual associations connected with place and time. Key: emotional content of stories and the retrieval situation.

- Memory cueing trials- spontaneous and reflective conditions.
- Spontaneous conditions: artist present with sitter during retrieval. Related dialogues: cues "surprises the unconscious", revealing less obvious memory stories.
- Responses allowing reflection. Sitter privately writes replies to triggers in personal "diary" over fixed period.

OUTCOMES

- Nature and type of artifacts produced not predetermined. But driven by the stories.
- Artistic Considerations: scale, form, texture, intimacy and functionality interpreted through symbols, metaphors, iconography including personal signifiers.
- Objects may be serviceable: adornment or vessels; artifacts may be purely contemplative: sculptural, talismanic.
- Narrative quality of new object should via metaphor or symbols be reflective of the original memory story/stories.

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CONCLUSIONS

- Autobiographical Memory (AM) - a collection of essential stories about our lives, critical to our identity, composed of scripts: dynamic frameworks - new memory stories indexed along with existing stories.
- Cherished objects (heirlooms - across generations) contain AM; cues to trigger memory stories.
- These are Evocative Objects : props to the scripts of our lives.
- Amygdala and Hippocampus: Limbic System elements processing memory retrieval and retention, and emotion - activated when presented with certain sensory cues. Olfactory and auditory inputs particularly effective stimuli.
- Sensory stimuli used to encourage memory story telling; also - time, place and relationships.
- Emotional value of original memory story, retrieval situation and relationship with artist all relevant.
- Common threads and patterns of personality and character examined and interpreted via symbols and metaphor.
- Material, form, structure, size and texture all significant interpretive elements in transformation from textual memory story to object. Goal : to endow new narrative object with distinctive meaning, reflective of the original memory story.